

THEORITICAL BASIS OF COMMUNICATIVE-COGNITIVE APPROACH
IN EFFECTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article reveals with the main aspects of motivational aspects and factors of communicative-cognitive method in teaching foreign language teaching effectively. Besides, it suggests the level, model of methods for developing the students’ attention to learn foreign language.

Key words: motivation, engagement, cooperative learning, educator needs, background knowledge, demonstration.

Issues of motivation, student engagement and participation can be heard from many educators. While a select few shine with these qualities, many students show the exact opposite. Embarrassment, fear and frustration are all emotions that can be seen in disengaged students.

Children who are engaged show enthusiasm, optimism, curiosity and interest. The opposite of engagement is disaffection. Disaffected children are passive, do not try hard, and give up easily in the fact of challenges, they can be bored, depressed, anxious or even angry about their presence in the classroom; they can be withdrawn from learning opportunities or even rebellious towards teachers and classmates.

Classrooms are full of both motivated and disaffected students. The focus of an educator needs be in shifting the negative attitudes and behaviors of their students to ones that are more intrinsically motivated and engaged.

According to Margolis and McCabe, “It is widely believed that without sufficiently high self-efficacy, or the belief that they can succeed on specific academic tasks such as homework, many struggling learners will not make the

effort needed to master academics”. Those students who have high self-efficacy participate more in class, persist through difficulties, and ultimately reach higher achievement. On the reverse side, students with low self-efficacy will not be motivated. Margolis and McCabe state that students with low self-efficiency will give up or avoid tasks similar to those previously failed. Therefore, teachers should not give tasks to the students that could promote anxiety of frustration. Teachers should be aware of their proper instructional and independent levels to make sure tasks are appropriate.

Research suggests that teachers can strengthen learner’s self-efficacy by teaching needed learning strategies, reinforcing effort and persistence, stressing peer modeling, teaching struggling learners to make facilitative attributions, and helping them identify personally important goals. Motivating learning strategies could include cooperative learning activities where students perform tasks well within their ability level, modeling, and sequencing tasks according to difficulty. Teachers may need to use reinforcers to initially motivate students. The teacher should use varying, small, natural reinforcers combined with common social and verbal reinforcers such as smiles, specific praise.

In order for the student to cultivate self-efficiency, they need to be in a nurturing, safe environment. A teacher can create such an environment by treating students with respect, showing interest in the students, and giving the students choices. The students will feel better about themselves and build self-efficacy when the teacher provides frequent, immediate, task-specific feedback, challenge rather than frustrate students, stress cooperation, not competition, make expectations clear and realistic. The students will then become engaged and thus be motivated by relating the curriculum to students’ interests, using a variety of teaching approaches to engage every student, stimulating curiosity, and engaging students in collaborative learning activities.

In addition to all of the environmental factors that can enhance motivation, it must essentially come from within the learner. It has been proven that intrinsically motivated students will persist through failure, take on more challenging tasks, use the creative process, and remain in tasks longer than those students with extrinsic motivation. Pederson found that students who participated in problem-based learning demonstrated higher rates of intrinsic motivation than during their regular classroom activities.

It can be clearly seen that the process of analyzing can educate the learners in the spirituality of strong responsibility on work which they are doing. The study researched sixth graders who used Alien Rescue, a computer-based problem based learning program. The students' motivation levels were compared during regular instruction and a computer-based problem-based learning unit. The study began with a teacher interview. The scale of Intrinsic versus Extrinsic Orientation in the Classroom which included five subscales was administered to the students before and after they used the computer program. The subscales included Preference for easy vs. challenging work, personal interest vs. pleasing the teacher, Dependent vs. independent mastery, and Reliance on teacher vs. independent judgment.

In problem-based learning (PBL), all of the learning comes from trying to solve a complex, authentic problem. The problems usually relate to everyday life and thus can produce student interest. During the solving process, students often collaborate with peers. The teacher acts as a facilitator who helps to examine the student's thinking and does not tell the student how to solve the problem.

With the same emphasis on student direction as problem-based learning, inquiry-focused learning is a process that cultivates in depth thinking, exploration, and enhanced student motivation. These ways of developing motivation among students suggested by Harada and Yoshina in 2004.

Inquiry-focused learning is outlined as follows:

a) Connect-connect to self and previous knowledge, gain background knowledge, observe and experience to gain an overview

b) Wonder-develop questions, make predictions and hypothesis

Investigate-find and evaluate information to answer questions and test hypotheses, think about the information to illuminate new questions and hypothesis

c) Construct-build new understandings, draw conclusions about questions and hypothesis

d) Express-communicate new ideas, apply understandings to a new context or situation

e) Reflect-reflect on one's own process of learning and new understandings gained from inquiry, pose new questions".

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